

Interplay between fast diffusion and molecular interaction in the formation of self-assembled nano-structures of S-Cysteine on Au(111).

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Abstract

We have studied the first stages leading to the formation of self-assembled monolayers of S-cysteine molecules adsorbed on Au(111) surface. Density Functional Theory (DFT) calculations for the adsorption of individual cysteine molecules on Au(111) at room temperature show low energy barriers all over the 2D Au(111) unit cell. As a consequence, cysteine molecules diffuse freely on the Au(111) surface and can be regarded as a 2D molecular gas. The balance between molecule-molecule and molecule-substrate interaction induces molecular condensation and evaporation from the morphological surface structures (steps, reconstruction edges, etc.) as revealed by Scanning Tunnelling Microscopy (STM) images. These processes lead progressively to the formation of a number of stable arrangements, not previously reported, like single-molecular rows, trimers and 2D islands. Condensation of these structures is driven by aggregation of new molecules, stabilized by the formation of electrostatic interactions between adjacent NH_3^+ and COO^- groups, together with adsorption at a slightly more favourable hollow-hcp site of the herring-bone Au reconstruction.

1. Introduction

Understanding the adsorption, bonding and interaction of the simplest constituents of proteins, amino acids, on surfaces is a necessary step towards broad applications in the interdisciplinary emerging field of nano-biotechnology. Self-assembled monolayers of different amino acids on well-controlled surfaces provide, for instance, convenient models to understand chiral selection mechanisms in the formation of higher ordered molecular structures,¹⁻² strategies to functionalize large molecular based nanostructures for solid state advanced biosensors³⁻⁴ or organic-inorganic platforms for new devices. The formation of highly ordered molecular self-assembled networks of amino acids on well-controlled metal surfaces have been previously studied.^{2,5} These molecular layers have been structurally analyzed and their chemical adsorption forms derived from these studies.⁶⁻⁸ However, very little is known about the mechanisms underlining the formation of those layers. A description at an atomistic level of those mechanisms is currently lacking, and deserves specific research. It requires a complete understanding of the energy balance between substrate-molecule and molecule-molecule interactions, which are better addressed in the submonolayer coverage regime. Thus, submonolayer deposition of amino acids, as cysteine, is an excellent framework to understand the self-assembling mechanisms leading to the formation of higher order structures out of their constituents. This is particularly interesting on the Au(111)-(22x√3) “herringbone” reconstruction, which include both hcp and fcc domain terminations with different adsorption energies.⁹ It is known that the zwitterionic form is preferred for cysteine on many different noble metal surfaces as Cu(110)⁷, Au(111)^{10,12-13} and Au(110)^{6,11-12}. However, the co-existence of other minor chemical adsorption forms (neutral, anionic or cationic) has been reported for other surface terminations and coverages,^{6,10,12-13} been their presence an unsolved puzzle.

Moreover, the study of submonolayer coverage makes feasible to address the role of the diffusion processes. Molecular diffusion mechanisms on surfaces are a key-point for nanoscale engineering to control the assembling of molecular rotors¹⁴ or other bio-objects. On the other hand, the S-Au bonding is technologically relevant because it is an important reference to understand the formation of Self-Assembled Monolayers (SAMs) of very different types. Thus, different proteins, nucleic acids or artificial peptides for technological applications are covalently bound to gold surfaces by sulfur atoms from cysteine moieties.^{4,15}

We shall show that, in the case of cysteine on Au(111), the substrate plays an important role defining the diffusion directions, the molecular orientations and, as a consequence, the different metastable molecular arrangements which are developed. We demonstrate hereafter that the diffusion barriers of the molecule are very small, and therefore fast directional molecular diffusion mechanisms are activated. These fast diffusion processes lead to the formation of different structures not previously reported, as cysteine trimers, molecular rows or ordered networks that evolve upon time towards 2D self-assembled molecular structures. We use a combination of Scanning Tunnelling Microscopy (STM) and Density Functional Theory (DFT) calculations to support our interpretation of experimental data. This combination of theoretical calculations with experimental techniques, allow us to describe an unreported diffusion process of these molecules on the surface, which is the basis of the understanding of the formation of self-assembled layers of amino acids on noble-metal surfaces.

Moreover, the enhanced diffusion of cysteine on the Au(111) surface makes it to behave as a 2D molecular gas.¹⁶ Adsorption and desorption from the different topographic features can be analyzed by recording real time sequenced STM images.

2. Experimental and theoretical methods.

In-situ multi-technique experiments have been performed (X-Ray Photoemission Spectroscopy (XPS), Ultraviolet Photoemission Spectroscopy (UPS), Low Energy Electron Diffraction (LEED) and STM) under ultra high vacuum conditions (base pressure of 1×10^{-10} mbar). The Au(111) crystal was cleaned by cycles of Ar^+ ion sputtering, flashing and annealing to ~ 700 K, the surface structure and cleanliness were monitored by LEED and STM before and after adsorption experiments. Before sublimation, the S-cysteine was outgassed and then heated to 373 K and exposed to the gold crystal. During the sublimation the main chamber pressure typically rose to 2×10^{-9} mbar. STM images were taken at room temperature using a commercial Omicron microscope combined with a Dulcinea electronics from *Nanotec Electronics*.¹⁷ Images were measured in constant-current mode (topographic mode) using a W-tip, with typical bias voltage value of -1.5 V (filled states of the sample) and tunnel currents of 0.3-0.4 nA. STM images were analyzed using the WSxM software.¹⁷

Calculations are performed using three complementary techniques: (i) a fast order-N real space approach,¹⁸ (ii) a thorough quantum-chemistry method based on a finite-cluster model and localized basis,¹⁹ and (iii) an accurate periodic supercell model based in a extended plane-waves basis.²⁰ The first method allow us to explore large systems made of many atoms and get quick estimates for expensive calculations like diffusion barriers of cysteine molecules adsorbed on the Au(111) surface. The second method

captures the essence of the local chemistry. It is, however, based on finite clusters with limited number of atoms and cannot model the metallic surface in its full complexity. Nonetheless it has helped us to build approximate geometrical models that yield reasonable input for more accurate formalisms based on periodic systems and plane-waves. Our order-N efficient DFT-local density approach (LDA) technique (FIREBALL code),²¹ which employs a basis formed by quasi-atomic orbitals that vanish for a cut-off radius¹⁸ the basis used here has been tested in previous publications.²²⁻²⁴ This method allows us to explore large systems made of many atoms with a good balance between the computational time consumed and the validity of the results. Notice that these amounts of realistic calculations are expensive if they are performed with a more accurate plane wave code. This is the reason we show only the FIREBALL results. In our calculations, we adsorb a single zwitterionic (deprotonated) molecule on different adsorption sites and with different orientations with respect to the Au(111)-surface. The supercell consists of a fcc stacked three layer slab with a 4x4 periodicity parallel to the surface. Under these conditions, we can assume that the molecule is isolated. We estimate the diffusion barriers by comparing the final energies after the system relaxation for different adsorbed sites and molecule orientations. Notice that these amounts of calculations are expensive if performed with a more accurate plane wave code. In each case, the last Au-layer and the (x,y) coordinates of the S in the molecule are fixed.

The computational effort necessary to perform these calculations with enough accuracy is very large, in particular if ab-initio methods based in properly converged plane-waves or full Linear Combination of Atomic Orbitals (LCAO) basis are used (e.g., our calculations with CASTEP or GAUSSIAN). This computational effort limits the

parameter space of configurations that can be explored. Therefore, we have used a complementary N-order method where a cutoff is introduced in the LCAO basis that allows us to explore a larger portion of configurations than before.

3. Results and discussion

Adsorption of S-cysteine on Au(111) surface takes place at the zwitterionic form in the submonolayer coverage regime,^{10,12-13} as also has been reported for Au(110).^{6,11-12} We have also confirmed by XPS spectra (data not shown) that at least 95% of the cysteine molecules adsorb on the gold surface as zwitterionic species. This information has been input for our DFT calculations that have assumed the zwitterionic species. As expected on chemical intuition grounds, our calculations for an isolated S-cysteine molecule on the Au(111) surface show that the bonding between the molecule and the surface takes place through the S atom. The optimized S-Au distance is about 0.255 nm and the most favourable adsorption position is near the hollow-hcp (see fig.1), in a configuration in which the oxygen atoms approach to the surface up to 0.26 nm, whereas the N atom is slightly detached from it. The two oxygen atoms of the carboxylate group are close to top position of Au atoms and the oxygen-gold interaction cannot be neglected. Therefore the molecule acquires a planar conformation, in agreement with the one experimentally determined by Cossaro et al. on Au(110).⁶ This double interaction of the molecule with the surface, throughout S and O, is a key point to determine the molecular azimuthal orientation. Previously, it has been reported using DFT that the preferential site for the S headgroup in cys/Au(111) is the bridge-fcc site.²⁵⁻²⁶ Di Felice found an S-Au distance of 0.251 nm,²⁵ however, contrary to us, they did not find a fairly planar structure for the adsorbed molecule.

By constrained optimization on different symmetry positions in the unit cell we have determined an upper value for the diffusion barrier of a single molecule. The result is shown in Fig. 1 together with the relative positions in the unit cell. The figure shows that the hollow-hcp site is the preferred one with adsorption energy slightly lower than the others, and particularly to that of the hollow-fcc site. However, the energy difference between all sites in the unit cell is small and the molecule is expected to diffuse quickly at room temperature following a path that goes from hollow-hcp to hollow-fcc through the top site with activation energy barriers of about 100 meV. We notice that diffusion barriers along the $[1\bar{1}0]$ surface direction are even smaller (lower than 60 meV). These calculated values are accurate within a 20%. The anisotropy in the energy barrier height induces a fast diffusion channel along this crystallographic direction at room temperature. Along the $[1\bar{1}2]$ direction higher barriers will make the molecules to reside longer times on the hollow-top region of the unit cell, slowing down their diffusion. Nonetheless, the overall low values for the diffusion barriers suggest that cysteine molecules can diffuse freely at room temperature throughout the Au surface. We will show next that many structural properties of the submonolayer coverage arrangements are related to these results.

STM images recorded right after depositing submonolayer coverage of S-cysteine molecules do not show any morphological feature on the surface related to the molecules. We exclusively observe spikes on the substrate terraces that correspond to molecules diffusing faster than the scan speed. A spike appears in the STM current every time a molecule moves underneath the STM tip. These fast-diffusing molecules could be imaged, however, at the step edges because the larger coordination produces a longer permanence time. We have to wait a few hours after dosing the molecule in order

to obtain STM images exhibiting molecular features. Interestingly, if we acquire successive images on the same area, video movies showing the time evolution of the different structures can be recorded [video movies showing cysteine diffusion are available as AVI]. Images in Figs. 2 and 3 are snapshots extracted from these videos and correspond to a general overview of the Au(111) surface after adsorption of about 0.4 ML of S-cysteine at $\sim 20^\circ\text{C}$. Many different molecular arrangements, disordered and ordered molecular structures are seen on the surface.⁵ The images shown in Fig. 2 are spaced by about 8 hours and those of Fig. 3 by 30 minutes. In the central part of the images of Fig. 2, anchored to the step edges, an area lacking of any order can be distinguished. The height of the features (about 0.2 nm) suggests that they are at the lower part of the steps. The shape and size of these areas evolve with time. Indeed we can consider these diffusing molecules throughout the surface as a 2D molecular gas, in which the surface plays the role of a solid support providing a reduced dimensionality to the system.¹⁶ In Figs. 2 and 3 it is shown how the molecules “*evaporate*” and “*condensate*” progressively on the different morphological structures (reconstruction corners and step edges). Interestingly, these morphological defects are not the final nucleation points, but just structures with a larger dwelling time where evaporation and condensation rates are similar. The nucleation points are on the terraces, where after some time the molecules meet each other, making groups of steady structures stabilized by H-bonds or electrostatic interactions. These are the truly nucleation sites in which the molecules from the 2D gas *condensate*. We see in the STM video movies that after few hours the molecules imaged at the step edges disappear in favour of the ordered structures. We have identified three stable types of morphological molecular assemblies that increase their extension with time: molecular wires, islands and trimers.

In all these cases the sulphur atom and the oxygen atoms of the carboxylate group from the cysteine interact with the Au surface.

Among all the stable structures we have identified, we describe first ordered single-molecular rows that can be observed between the channels of the characteristic Au(111)-(22x√3) “herringbone” reconstruction, as shown in Fig. 4. We observe preferential binding of the molecules on the fcc domains of the Au(111) surface reconstruction.⁹ The wires are formed along the [110] surface direction. This can be understood from our DFT calculations, as illustrated in Fig. 5. The [110] direction is the faster diffusing molecular channel, therefore the molecules are likely to meet each other preferentially along this direction. The blue arrow in Fig. 5 indicates this direction. During the diffusion they reside longer at hollow-hcp sites. When a diffusing molecule meets another they establish electrostatic interactions between the carboxylate group of a molecule (negatively charged) and the amino group of the other (positively charged). We estimate the distance between these chemical groups to be 0.28 nm, which is in good agreement with the reported value 0.25-0.29 nm for the NH···O hydrogen bond (donor-acceptor).²⁷⁻²⁸ Fig. 5 shows the optimized DFT structure of this configuration, in which hydrogen bonds and electrostatic forces between carboxylate and amine groups stabilize the structure. We have encircled in the figure the interaction established between adjacent molecules. Furthermore, this configuration presents another interesting point: the O atoms of the carboxylate groups match near-top position with respect to the Au surface, which helps further to stabilize the structure. As a consequence, molecules diffusing along [110] directions bind to each other, and stay on this favourable site. These clusters are seeds for further molecules to be aggregated. The wire growing direction is the [110] direction, as it has been suggested by our

calculations and corroborated experimentally. This is schematically represented in Fig. 5. Thus, we can conclude that the mechanism of formation of these wires is aggregation by diffusion. Remarkably, in the Au(110) face it has been observed the formation of paired rows of cysteine molecules through O-H \cdots O bonding.²⁹ The authors also described a mechanism based in fast diffusion and the formation of different dimers oriented along crystallographic directions. Unlike results on the (110) face, in our case the NH \cdots O bond is preferred because of the role played by the substrate. In the (111) face, the molecule has an optimum size to coordinate with the Au substrate atoms by both sulphur and the carboxylate group, and at the same time one of the oxygen atoms can establish interactions with the NH group of an adjacent molecule (see Fig.5). In any case, we have calculated the formation of a dimer stabilised by two OH \cdots O bridges. In the dimer, the molecules share two OH \cdots O bonds whereas in the trimer NH \cdots O interactions are involved. Unlike the (110) face, and similarly to our previous discussion of the rows, the three-fold symmetry of the substrate induces trimer formation instead of dimers. Our calculations indicate that no stable bridging structures can be formed. Therefore, we conclude that in the Au(111) face the interaction with the surface induce the formation of single molecular rows instead of the dimers reported for the (110) face.

The morphology and length of these wires is small and they appear broken in a zig-zag conformation (Figure 4). We have experimentally verified that these wires do not traverse towards the hcp domain of the herringbone reconstruction, but they remain in the fcc part of the reconstruction.⁹ Indeed the molecular wire increases their length by aggregation, as discussed above, until it approaches the change of atomic registry at the border of the domain. Here, the molecule modifies its adsorption site by shifting about two atomic rows towards the fcc side of the reconstruction. This rectification

mechanism confers to the molecular rows the zig-zag appearance observed by STM (see Fig. 4). Thus, cysteine assembled unimolecular wires slightly re-orientate their position to accommodate the main chain direction along the $[1\bar{1}2]$ surface direction. This reorientation is possible because the low diffusion barriers depicted in Fig.1. The meandering conformation of the wires is therefore related to a delicate balance between the molecule-substrate interaction, which favours adsorption on the fcc sites of the reconstruction, and the molecule-molecule interaction that favors molecular row packing along the $[1\bar{1}0]$ surface direction, establishing H-bonding networks between adjacent molecules. Molecular preferential adsorption on fcc domains has been reported for many different molecular systems (as C₆₀ or PCBM molecular layers). The reason for this preferential nucleation may be both steric (the fcc areas are wider than the hcp ones) and/or electronic (the charge density of the surface-state electrons is different in fcc/hcp regions and in the dislocation lines of the reconstruction).³⁰⁻³⁶

We also observe islands of molecules (i.e., 2D ordered structure of molecules) appearing on the surface after a certain time. They are formed by molecular parallel rows, separated by 1.25 nm (0.6 nm between adjacent molecules) and running along the $[1\bar{1}0]$ direction. Here we report, for the first time, the formation of this particular ordered structure. Previously it was reported the existence of ordered phases of cysteine molecules exhibiting a quadratic symmetry configuration.⁵ Indeed, we have found this surface crystallographic phase for slightly higher substrate temperatures (35-40°C). Our 2D-islands, however, are the final *condensation* form of the 2D molecular gas. As shown in the series of consecutive images of Fig. 3, 2D-islands are the sole structures to increase their size with time, becoming the most stable structure 24 hours after deposition.

Finally, of particular interest are the features imaged at the reconstruction elbows. We can distinguish two types of features: blurred and defined. The fuzzy features consist of spikes along the scanning direction and are imaged on top of the reconstruction elbows. They could correspond to diffusing molecules of the 2D-molecular-gas that are observed in the STM images because of a longer dwelling time on this favourable position of the surface.^{14,27} Some of them can be observed in the square marked area in Figure 2. Moreover, in the figure we also observe groups of well-defined molecular features with triangular shape (marked with circles). A detail of these structures is shown in Figure 6. We observe three molecular features imaged between the elbows of the Au herringbone reconstruction and, inside the fcc side of the surface reconstruction. The separation between the bumps is about 1.7 nm and they have a triangular shape with a depression in the middle. They are always imaged with the same orientation with respect to the surface and their number increase with time as shown in Fig 2 (encircled features). They also correspond to stable structures. Their formation must be related to an extra longer dwelling time when approaching the reconstruction corner, which could promote H-bonds interactions, leading to the stabilization of these structures.

However, the size and separation between bumps is large to be formed by a single molecule, and therefore they have to be constituted by a molecular aggregation. Indeed, in some images, they seem also to be formed by three other bumps. As shown in Fig. 6 we propose a tentative model based in distances derived from our STM images and the likely interactions to be found on such large objects as the trimers. The terminating strong polar carboxylate group interacts with the NH_3^+ groups to stabilize three cysteine molecules. Thus each of the three bumps observed correspond to three molecules, as

can be inferred from the ball and stick model overimposed on the STM image of a trimer structure. The hydrogen bond distance in these structures is 0.28 nm, similar to that found in the molecular rows. In our simulations these structures cannot be formed by just a pair of cysteine molecules, because we have observed the formation of H-bonds where a hydrogen is almost resonating between two molecules.³⁰ In the dimer the molecule share two OH \cdots O hydrogen bonds whereas in the trimer three NH \cdots O bonds are involved. Unlike the (110) face, and similarly to our previous discussion of the rows, the three-fold symmetry of the substrate induces trimer formation instead of dimers.

It is important to remark that the distance between molecular trimers is 1.7 nm. This distance is far too large to promote formation of S-S dimers connecting them. These molecular trimers separate apart of each other and cluster in a trimeric structure, occupying the whole length of the fcc domain of the Au reconstruction. Thus, the interaction stabilizing the large trimeric structure is driven by long-range van der Waals forces combined with the chemical interaction with the substrate. At present we do not have a satisfactory explanation for the assembly in three molecular groups. Similar molecular structures formed by related mechanisms have recently been reported to lead to arrays of single molecule rotors on the Au surface.¹⁴

4. Conclusions

Highly diffusing cysteine molecules on the Au surface can be regarded as a 2D molecular gas. Continue molecular condensation and evaporation from the

morphological surface defects, as reconstruction kinks or steps edges, leads progressively to the formation of stable arrangements, as unimolecular rows, trimers and 2D islands, where the molecules condensate in stable structures. The condensation process is driven by the formation of stable NH \cdots O electrostatic interactions between adjacent molecules together with both, adsorption of the sulphur atom in the slightly more favourable site at the hollow-hcp site of the Au reconstruction and one of the oxygen atoms of the carboxylate group sitting near a top site.

Acknowledgment

Work carried out at CAB was supported by the European Union, Instituto Nacional de Técnica Aeroespacial, Ministerio de Ciencia e Innovación (MICIN) and Comunidad de Madrid. We acknowledge funding through the Spanish research projects MAT-2008-1497 and CSD 2007-41. Dr.C.G. acknowledges the CSIC contract under the program JAE cofunded by FSE.

References

- (1) Kuhnle, A.; Linderoth, T.R.; Hammer, B.; Besenbacher, F. *Nature* **2002**, *415*, 891.
- (2) Raval, R. *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2009**, *38*, 707.
- (3) Mateo-Marti, E.; Briones, C.; Pradier, C.M.; Martín-Gago, J.A. *Biosensors and Bioelectronics* **2007**, *22*, 1926.
- (4) Briones, C.; Martín-Gago, J.A. *Current Nanoscience*, **2006**, *2*, 257.
- (5) Kuhnle, A.; Linderoth, T.R.; Schunack, M.; Besenbacher, F. *Langmuir* **2006**, *22*, 2156.

- (6) Cossaro, A.; Terreni, S.; Cavalleri, O.; Prato, M.; Cvetko, D.; Morgante, A.; Floreano, L.; Canepa, M. *Langmuir* **2006**, *22*, 11193.
- (7) Mateo Marti, E.; Methivier, Ch.; Pradier, C.M. *Langmuir* **2004**, *20*, 10223.
- (8) Barlow, S.; Raval, R. *Current Opinion in Colloid & Interface Science* **2008**, *13*, 65.
- (9) Guo, Q.; Yin, F.; Palmer, R E. *Small* **2005**, *1*, 76.
- (10) Cavalleri, O.; Gonella, G.; Terreni, S.; Vignolo, M.; Floreano, L.; Morgante, A.; Canepa, M.; Rolandi, R. *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **2004**, *6*, 4042.
- (11) Gonella, G.; Terreni, S.; Cvetko, D.; Cossaro, A.; Mattera, L.; Cavalleri, O.; Rolandi, R.; Morgante, A.; Floreano, L.; and Canepa, M. *J. Phys. Chem. B* **2005**, *109*, 18003.
- (12) Canepa, M.; Lavagnino, L.; Pasquali, L.; Moroni, R.; Bisio, F.; De Renzi, V.; Terreni, S.; and Mattera, L. *J. Phys.: Condens. Matter* **2009**, *21*, 264005.
- (13) De Renzi, V.; Lavagnino, L.; Corradini, V.; Biagi, R.; Canepa, M.; and del Pennino, U. *J. Phys. Chem C* **2008**, *112*, 14439.
- (14) L Gao, Q Liu, Y Y Zhang, N Jiang, H G Zhang, Z H Cheng, W F Qiu, S X Du, Y Q Liu, W A Hofer, H-J Gao. *Phys Rev Lett* **2008**, *101*, 197209.
- (15) Vericat, C.; Vela, M.E.; Benitez, G.A.; Martin-Gago, J.A.; Torrelles, X.; Salvarezza, R.C. *J.Phys: Condens. Matter* **2006**, *18*, R867.
- (16) Stranick, S J.; Kamma, M M.; Weiss, P S. *Science* **1994**, *266*, 99.
- (17) Horcas, I.; Fernandez, R.; Gomez-Rodriguez, J.M.; Colchero, J.; Gomez-Herrero, J.; Baro, A.M. *Rev. Sci. Instrum.* **2007**, *78*, 013705. <http://www.nanotec.es>.
- (18) Sankey, O.F.; Niklewski, D.J. *Phys. Rev. B* **1989**, *40*, 3979.
- (19) Frisch, M.J.; Trucks, G.W.; Schlegel, H.B.; Scuseria, G.E.; Robb, M.A.; *Rev. C.* **2004**, *02*.
- (20) Clark, S.J.; Segall, M. D.; Pickard, C.J.; et al. *Z. fuer Kristallographie*, **2005**, *220*, 567. <http://www.accelrys.com>
- (21) P.Jelinek *et al.* *Phys Rev B* **2005**, *71*, 235191.
- (22) Otero, G.; Biddau, G.; Sánchez-Sánchez, C.; Caillard, R.; López, M. F.; Rogero, C.; Palomares, F. J.; Basanta, M.A.; Ortega, J.; Mendez, J.; Echavarren, A. M.; Pérez, R.; Gómez-Lor B.; Martín-Gago, J.A. *Nature* **2008**, *454*, 865.
- (23) González, C.; Ortega, J.; Flores, F.; Martínez-Martín, D.; Gómez-Herrero, J. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **2009**, *102*, 106801.
- (24) Betti, M.G.; Kanjilal, A.; Mariani, C.; et al. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **2008**, *100*, 027601.
- (25) Di Felice, R.; Selloni, A.; Molinari, E. *J. Phys. Chem. B* **2003**, *107*, 1151.

- (26) Nazmutdinov, R.R.; Manyurov, I.R.; Zinkicheva, T.T.; Jang, J.; Ulstrup, J. *Russian Journal of Electrochemistry* **2007**, *43*, 32.
- (27) Gu, Z.; Ridenour, C.F.; Bronnimann, Ch. E.; Iwashita, T.; McDermott, A. *Journal of American Chemical Society* **1996**, *118*, 822.
- (28) Baker, E.N.; Hubbard, R.E. *Prog Biophys. molec. Biol.* **1984**, *44*, 97.
- (29) Kuhnle, A.; Molina, L.M.; Linderoth, T. R.; Hammer, B.; Besenbacher, F. *Phys Rev Lett* **2004**, *93*, 086101.
- (30) Böhringer, M.; Morgenstern, K.; Schneider, W-D.; Berndt, R.; Mauri, F.; De Vita, A.; Car, R. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **1999**, *83*, 324.
- (31) Altman, E. I.; Colton, R. J. *Surf. Sci.* **1992**, *279*, 49.
- (32) Fujita, D.; Yakabe, T.; Nejoh, H.; Sato T.; Iwatsuki, M. *Surf. Sci.* **1996**, *366*, 93.
- (33) Ecija, D.; Otero, R.; Sánchez, L.; Gallego, J.M.; Wang, Y.; Alcamí, M.; Martín, F.; Martín, N.; Miranda, R. *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2007**, *46*, 7874.
- (34) Sánchez, L.; Otero, R.; Gallego, J.M.; Miranda, R.; Martín, N. *Chem Rev.* **2009**, *109*, 2081.
- (35) Kroger, J.; Neel, N.; Jensen, H.; Berndt, R.; Rurali, R.; Lorente, N. *J. Phys.: Condens. Matter* **2006**, *18*, S51.
- (36) Vladimirova, M.; De Vita, A.; Pimpinelli, A. *Phys. Rev. B* **2001**, *64*, 245420.

Figures Captions

Figure 1 .- Energy Landscape for a cysteine molecule on different sites of the Au(111) unit cell. Calculations have been performed considering a cysteine molecule on a 3 layers slab with a 4x4 periodicity. In each site, we show the best energy value obtained when the molecule has been rotated in several azimuthal orientations and in z-direction.

Figure 2.- Series of STM images extracted from a video (image size 116nmx116nm). In a blue square is marked one of the diffusing cysteine molecules at the elbows of the Au(111) reconstruction and in the two green circles the formation of trimer molecular structures can be distinguished.

Figure 3.- Series of STM images (image size 66nmx66nm) extracted from a video showing the formation of stable and extended 2D islands formed by cysteine wires after long diffusing time.

Figure 4.- STM images (35nmx22 nm, upper panel, 71nmx36nm, lower panel) showing cysteine single molecule wires on the Au(111) reconstructed surface for submonolayer coverage. Preferential adsorption at fcc domains of the Au reconstruction is clearly observed.

Figure 5.- Upper part: schematic model of the cysteine adsorption DFT. The arrow indicates the diffusion direction and the circle the interaction established to form the molecular wires along the $[1\bar{1}0]$ direction. Lower part: STM image (image size 26nmx21nm) showing a step edge and in the lower terrace single-molecule cysteine wires running along this $[1\bar{1}0]$ direction with a preferential adsorption at the fcc part of the reconstruction.

Figure 6. -Detail of the trimer structures and DFT calculated configurations (the structure position over the STM image (image size 16nm \times 7nm) is only a guide).

